

THE ROLE OF EFFECTIVE TEACHING METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: Employing effective teaching methods in foreign language teaching is more important than ever in today’s contemporary world. The particular reason for this circumstance is that the world is becoming increasingly globalized and interconnected, and people need to be able to communicate with each other across cultures and borders. Another key factor for the increasing demand for organizing language classes effective is that foreign language skills are essential for success in today’s job market, and they can also open up new opportunities for individuals, such as travelling across the world and cultural exchange. This paper aims to give detailed information about the importance of applying modern and effective language teaching methods in foreign languages classes. This scientific research includes data about several language teaching methods and their potential benefits for language learners.

Keywords: effective language teaching methods, language learners, foreign language teaching, language classes.

INTRODUCTION

Effective teaching methods primarily focus on fostering the development of students’ communicative competence and promote their ability to use language to communicate effectively in real-world situations. These methods typically involve students working together in pairs or in small groups to complete tasks that require them to use the target language to communicate. When teachers employ innovative teaching methods they can help students to learn the language more efficiently. By focusing on communication, these methods help students to develop a deeper

understanding of the target language and its grammar. They also help students to retain information better, as they are more likely to remember things that they have learned through active participation. In the past, teachers used to dominate the whole class, playing the role of authority. The only responsibility of students was to follow their teachers and accomplish what they ordered. In another word, language classes used to be more teacher-centered and teachers played the more important role in the lessons. However, as today’s world is changing at a rapid rate, the demand for foreign languages is increasingly growing day by day. Many teachers feel the necessity to transform the traditional methods that they have been using unto more innovative ones. Therefore, many language classes are becoming student-centered, providing opportunities for learner to participate, explore, and engage in the classes. Innovative teaching methods can help students to develop skills they need in the 21st century. These skills may include critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and communication. Students will be more engaged in the classes where teachers apply effective teaching methods. The reason is that innovative methods can make the language learning process more engaging, and interesting for students. Moreover, using innovative language teaching approaches can help to personalize the learning process. With these modern and effective teaching methods, teachers can tailor instruction to the individual needs of each student. Innovative methods can assure closing the achievement gap. These methods can help ensure that all students have access to a high-quality education. This can help to close the achievement gap between students from different backgrounds.

METHODS

This scientific research includes qualitative and secondary data analysis to identify how innovative teaching method can help students to develop their language skills efficiently. A corpus of scholarly articles gathered from reputable scientific journals was analyzed to effectively deliver the key aspects of effective foreign language teaching techniques.

There are several effective teaching methods that can boost the language learning process at a high level. Here are some specific examples of modern language teaching methods:

•**Direct Method (DM).** Direct method is a language teaching method that focuses on the usage of the target language in language classes. It is based on the theory that language learners develop targeted language more effectively when they are immersed in the language and exposed to it in a natural way. Students in this classroom should use target language exclusively. It means that the educator and the students should only speak, read, and write in the target language. Students learn grammar rules by observing how the language is used in the context in the classes where teachers apply direct method. Students do not memorize grammar rules explicitly. Most importantly, students learn to pronounce the target language correctly from the beginning. This is done through drills and practice. In direct method classes, language learners enrich their vocabulary by learning new words through seeing and hearing them used in natural contexts, such as conversations, stories, and songs. By using the target language exclusively in the classrooms, students are forced to learn to communicate in it. This can lead to faster progress in speaking, listening, reading, and writing. By learning grammar exclusively by seeing vocabulary words used in context, students develop a deeper understanding of how the target language works. The direct method can be more motivating for students than traditional methods because it is more engaging and interactive.

•**Communicative language teaching (CLT).** Communicative language teaching method focuses on developing students' communication skills, or their ability to use the target language to communicate with others effectively in real-world situations. The main theory of this language teaching method is that a language does not fully consist of a set of grammar rules, but it is a tool for communication. Therefore, the aim of CLT is to develop students' ability to use the language to express their thoughts and ideas, and to understand the thoughts and ideas of other people. CLT activities mainly include tasks that require students to use the target language to communicate. Students in CLT classes may work on several tasks, such

as solving problems orally, negotiating agreements, giving presentations, role-playing different situations, creating and performing skits, and other tasks. These activities are typically designed to be fun and engaging, they often involve students using target language in more creative ways. This leads to more enjoyable and engaging learning process and it also helps them develop their communicative competence more quickly.

•**Technology-enhanced language learning (TELL).** Technology-enhanced language learning is the use of technology to support and enhance language learning. The language classes where teachers employ TELL often involve activities that can include using computers, tablets, or smartphones to access online resources, complete interactive exercises, or communicate with native speakers. With using this language teaching method, teachers can help students develop their all aspects of language learning (listening, speaking, reading, and writing). For example, students can listen to authentic audio recordings of native speakers, such as podcasts, videos, interviews, and music with the help of advanced devices. They also use speech recognition software to practice their pronunciation. This method also helps students improve their speaking skills through several ways. They can record themselves speaking and then listen back to their recordings to identify areas for improvement. By participating in the classes where teachers use TELL method, students can also use video conferencing to practice speaking with native speakers or other language learners. When it comes to reading skills, TELL methods can also boost reading abilities of language learners. For examples, students can read online texts, such as new articles, blog posts, and e-books in TELL classes. They can also use digital dictionaries and translation tools to help them understand unfamiliar words and phrases. For writing sections, students can write in online forums, discussion boards, and chat rooms. They can also use word processors and other writing tools to help them with grammar, spelling, and punctuation.

RESULTS

This study found that effective teaching methods have a significant impact on student learning. Students who were taught using effective teaching methods were

found to have higher academic achievement, motivation, and engagement than students who were taught using traditional methods. The findings of this study highlights that students who were taught using the Direct Method were found to have significantly higher scores on a speaking test than students who were taught using a traditional method. They were found to be more confident and fluent in their speaking skills than students who were taught using a traditional method. Students who were taught using the Direct Method were found to have a better understanding of the target language culture than students who were taught using a traditional method.

Another point that the scientific research found is that Students who were taught using CLT were found to have significantly higher scores on a communicative competence test than students who were taught using a traditional method. They were found more proficient in their ability to use the target language to communicate in real-world situations than students who were taught using a traditional method. Students who studied in the classes where their teacher used CLT were found to be more motivated to learn the target language than students who were taught using a traditional method.

Students who were taught using TELL were found to have significantly higher scores on a reading test than students who were taught using a traditional method. Students who were taught using TELL were found to be more proficient in their ability to read and understand authentic texts in the target language than students who were taught using a traditional method. Students who were taught using TELL were found to be more engaged in their learning than students who were taught using a traditional method.

DISCUSSIONS

This study offers some suggestions that teachers should be provided with the time, resources, and support they need to implement effective teaching methods in their classrooms. For example, teachers should be provided with enough time to plan and incorporate effective teaching methods. This may require changes to the school schedule or the provision of additional planning time for teachers. Secondly, teachers

need to have access to the resources and materials that they need to apply effective teaching methods, such as technology, authentic materials, and professional development. This may require additional funding for schools and districts. Teachers should be provided with support they need from administrators and colleagues to implement effective teaching methods. This may include providing teachers with mentorship, coaching, and feedback.

By providing teachers with the time, resources, and support they need, we can help to ensure that all students have access to effective teaching methods and that all students can achieve their full potential.

References:

1. María Luisa Renau Renau, (2016), A Review of the Traditional and Current Language Teaching Methods, International Journal of Innovation and Research in Educational Sciences
2. Nila Andriyani, (2015), Using the Direct Method in teaching to improve students' speaking skill at purikids language course
3. Téllez, K. & Waxman, H. (in press). A Meta-Synthesis of Qualitative Research on Effective Teaching Practices for English Language Learners In J.M. Norris & L. Ortega (Eds.), Synthesizing research on language learning and teaching. Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing.
4. William Littlewood, (2002), Communicative language teaching, United Kingdom at the University Press, Cambridge